

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 9; September 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

It is with pleasure that I present to you today a special issue on Internet-related papers. All of the five papers in this issue are extended versions of WebNet'96 conference contributions (San Francisco, Oct.15-19, 96). The papers have been selected with the permission of AACE, the organisation responsible for WebNet, and have been revised and extended by the authors for J.UCS. Each of the papers has received a best paper award, i.e. obtained the highest marks possible from each of 3 referees: Thus, I am sure you will enjoy reading them.

I would like to thank the authors for being willing to adapt the papers for J.UCS, and AACE for the permission to publish extended versions in J.UCS.

For details on the conference (if you read this early in October you still even have a chance to attend the conference!), or for the proceedings in printed or CD ROM form contact the Association for Advancement of Computers in Education at aace@virginia.edu, or see <http://www.aace.org>.

Let me also mention that the October issue will have Professor Patricia Carlson from Rose-Hulman Institute of Technology, USA as guest editor with contributions on "The classroom of the future". So don't forget to look up J.UCS again in a month's time ... and please do consider J.UCS for publication of some of your high-quality papers.

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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